

Buckling behavior of CFRP-steel composite columns under temperature variation

Xu Liang, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China, liang-xu@sjtu.edu.cn
Lili Hu*, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, China, lilihu@sjtu.edu.cn
Peng Feng, Tsinghua University, China, fengpeng@tsinghua.edu.cn

ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber-reinforced polymer (CFRP) stress variation caused by temperature has a significant influence on the buckling behavior of prestressed CFRP-reinforced steel columns. This paper first revealed the temperature effect mechanism on such columns. Then numerical analysis was conducted with different initial CFRP prestress and preloading under temperature variation (20 to 80/-80 °C), including transient and steady analysis. The results show that in steady analysis, the buckling capacity remains almost unchanged; in transient analysis, the buckling capacity can decrease as much as 18% under temperature variation and the high temperature effect with a larger preloading or prestress is more significant.

This paper was presented at CICE and published as follows:

Hu, L.L., Liang, X., Feng, P., Li, H.T. (2023). Temperature effect on buckling behavior of prestressed CFRP-reinforced steel columns. *Thin Wall Struct* 188, 110879.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tws.2023.110879>

KEYWORDS

Temperature effect, composite structures, steel column, buckling

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.